

THERMOPLASTIC MONO-MATERIAL SANDWICH PANELS

Manufacturing for aircraft interiors

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AGENDA

- About Diehl Aviation
- Object and concept
- Manufacturing process
- Numerical method
- Isothermal process
- Non-isothermal process
- Combined process
- Bonding degree
- Summary and outlook

DIEHL AVIATION

Conventional sandwich structure:

- phenolic/epoxy glass fiber reinforced prepregs
- aramid-phenolic resin paper honeycomb core (NOMEX®)

OBJECT AND CONCEPT

- obtain an adhesion-free thermoplastic sandwich panel
- challenge: to get a sufficient bonding degree between skins and honeycomb core by means of fusion bonding
- define optimal manufacturing process

MANUFACTURING PROCESS

■ Isothermal process

■ Non-isothermal process

■ Combined process

NUMERICAL METHOD

ISOTHERMAL PROCESS

ISOTHERMAL PROCESS

NON-ISOTHERMAL PROCESS

NON-ISOTHERMAL PROCESS

- Contact with cold pressing tools
- T_{skin} drops fast
- $T_{skin} > T_g$ app. 3 sec
- $T_{core} < 60^\circ\text{C}$, no risk of core collapse

NON-ISOTHERMAL PROCESS

NON-ISOTHERMAL PROCESS

NON-ISOTHERMAL PROCESS

COMBINED PROCESS

MICROSCOPY

Isothermal process

- Core is partially melted and pressed
- Domination of melted part
- Bonding degree is determined by contact surface

Non-isothermal process

- Skin is heated
- Core penetration in softened skin
- Partial melting of core
- Bonding degree is defined by penetration depth and contact surface

DRUM PEEL TEST

Drum peel test is conducted to determine the bonding quality between a face sheet and honeycomb core of the sandwich compound (ASTM D 1781).

Isothermal process
Peel resistance 2 N/mm

Non-isothermal process
Peel resistance 6 N/mm

SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Thermal analysis

Definition of process window for:

- 1) Isothermal process
- 2) non-isothermal process (with restriction)
- 3) Combined process

Thermo-mechanical analysis

- 1) Mechanical behavior during thermoforming process
- 2) Failure modes prediction
- 3) Process window optimization

Thank you!

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